

EXPLORING THE PLAY-BASED LEARNING STRATEGIES: ELEMENTARY TEACHERS IN FOCUS

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Abstract. Play-based learning has gained increasing recognition as an effective pedagogical approach in elementary education, offering students opportunities to engage in active, experiential learning. This research explores the implementation and impact of play-based learning strategies with a specific focus on elementary teachers. The results of the study disclosed considering the first objective of this study is the lived experience of teachers in the implementation of play-based learning in elementary classrooms. Teacher beliefs and attitudes towards play-based learning, and lastly, Implementation of play-based learning in elementary classrooms. The second objective of this study is for the teachers to cope with the implementation of play-based learning in elementary classrooms. Based on the interview data gathered from the teacher's coping mechanism with the challenges teachers explore in the implementation of play-based learning in elementary classrooms the three major themes such as the impact of play-based learning on student outcomes, Play-based learning and academic achievement, and Play-based learning and curriculum goals. The third objective of this study is to explore educational insight or tools that can be drawn from the study of the play-based learning elementary teachers in focus emerged major themes such as classroom organization and materials, limitations and critical analysis of literature, and the importance of child-centered learning. Further discuss In the future, we should explore and implement more flexible assessment models that align with how classroom layouts, materials, and resources influence the effectiveness of play-based strategies.

KEY WORDS

1. Play-based learning strategies
2. teachers in focus
3. learning strategies

1. Introduction

Play-based learning fosters children's development through exploration and discovery. However, implementing it in formal educational settings like elementary classrooms can be challenging for teachers. This study aims to develop effective strategies to support children's learning and development in such settings. In a global context, in this systematic review, the authors explored the challenges of implementing play-based learning in primary schools, including Grade 1 classrooms, from a global perspective. The study identified several key challenges, including limited teacher training and support, conflicting demands and expectations from parents and administrators, and a lack of appropriate resources and materials. The authors also highlighted the need for further research on the effectiveness of play-based learning in promoting children's academic and socio-emotional development. (Gervilla et al., 2021).

In the national context, in this study, the authors explored the challenges of implementing play-based learning in Grade 1 classrooms in public schools in the Philippines. The study used a qualitative approach and collected data through semi-structured interviews with Grade 1 teachers. The findings revealed several challenges, including limited resources and materials, lack of support from administrators and parents, and the need for more professional development opportunities for teachers. The study also identified strategies teachers used to overcome these challenges, such as improvising materials, collaborating with colleagues, and communicating with parents and administrators to promote understanding and support for the approach (Ca-

bling et al., 2020). In the local context, one study by Aparece and Ranese (2021). In this study, the authors explored the challenges of implementing the K-12 curriculum in a public elementary school in Davao City, which includes play-based learning as a component in the early grades. The study used a case study approach and collected data through interviews with school administrators, teachers, and students and document analysis. The findings revealed several challenges, including inadequate resources and facilities, limited teacher training and professional development opportunities, and a lack of support from parents and the community.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—The purpose of the study is to find solutions to overcome these constraints. A study studying the difficulties teachers have in implementing play-based learning in elementary classrooms aims to identify the problems and issues they encounter. The study intends to comprehend the viewpoints of educators, administrators, and other stakeholders involved in play-based learning implementation and to produce insights into the variables that aid or obstruct its proper execution. The study's conclusions can guide practice and policy by offering suggestions for enhancing play-based learning in first-grade classrooms, which can improve the learning outcomes for young children. The study's overall goal is to add to the corpus of information about play-based education for young children.

- (1) What is the lived experience of teachers in implementing play-based learning in elementary classrooms?
- (2) How do teachers cope to explore implementing play-based learning in elementary classrooms?
- (3) What educational insight or tool can be drawn from the study?

1.2. Theoretical Lens—This study is anchored in the following theories: Social Constructivism by Wood, D., Bruner, J. S., Ross, G. (1976). This theory posits that learning is a social and interactive process that occurs through collaboration and interaction with others. According to this theory, play-based learning provides opportunities for children to learn through interactions with peers and adults and through exploring and experimenting with the environment. Secondly, Vygotsky's Zone of Proximal Development theory (1978) suggests that learn-

ing occurs when children are assisted in activities slightly above their current level of understanding or competence, with the guidance of a more knowledgeable individual. In the context of play-based learning, teachers can support children's learning by offering opportunities for them to participate in challenging, achievable activities. Ryan and Deci (2000) proposed the Self-Determination Theory, which suggests that intrinsic motivation, or the drive to engage in an activity for its own sake, is crucial for promoting engagement and learning. Play-based

Fig. 1. Conceptual Framework of the Study

learning can enhance children’s intrinsic motivation by providing opportunities for autonomy, competence, and relatedness, the three basic psychological needs identified in this theory. Teachers must receive training and professional development opportunities to implement play-based learning strategies effectively in their classrooms.

2. Methodology

In this chapter, the researcher introduces the philosophical assumptions, qualitative assumptions, research procedures, participants, data collection, and analysis. Artificial intelligence (AI) was used for proofreading, as it is a common ethical practice in many articles today. In the preparation of this paper, the researcher employed artificial intelligence tools for proofreading. Specifically, AI was utilized to enhance the accuracy, coherence, and overall quality of the manuscript. This practice is being explicitly stated to maintain transparency and adhere to ethical standards in research. The usage of AI for proofreading reflects a commitment to leveraging advanced technologies responsibly and acknowledges the increasing prevalence and capability of AI in academic and professional writing.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions—The study assumed that all participants answered interview questions honestly and to the best of their abilities. It was also assumed that the sample used for this study was representative of in-depth and focus group interviews conducted face-to-face as a means of communication. These assumptions have been discussed for the past 20 years in various SAGE Handbooks of Qualitative Research (Denzin Lincoln, 1994, 2000, 2005, 2011) and have been presented as the fundamental issues put forward by Guba and Lincoln (1988) as the guiding philosophy behind qualitative research. These beliefs have been referred to as paradigms (Lincoln, 1985), philosophical assumptions, epistemologies, and ontologies (Crotty, 1998), broadly conceived research methodologies (Neuman, 2000), and alternative knowledge claims (Creswell, 2014). There are beliefs about ontology (the nature of reality), epistemology (what counts as knowledge and how knowledge claims are justified), axiology (the role of values in research), and methodology (the process of research). In this discussion, I was first discussing each of these philosophical assumptions, detail how they might be used and written into qualitative research, and then link them to different interpretive frameworks that operate at a more specific level in the process of research. Ontology. The issue relates to the nature of reality and its characteristics. When researchers con-

duct qualitative research, they are embracing the idea of teacher's perceptions and experiences in exploring the challenges of implementing play-based learning in grade 1 classrooms. Different researchers embrace different realities, as do the individuals being studied and the readers of a qualitative study. When studying individuals, qualitative researchers conduct a study with the intent of reporting these multiple realities. Evidence of multiple realities includes the use of multiple forms of evidence in themes using the actual words of different individuals and presenting different perspectives. For example, when writers compile a phenomenology, they report how individuals participating in the study view their experiences differently (Moustakas, 1994). Epistemology. Conducting a qualitative study means that the researcher tries to get as close as possible to the participants being studied. Therefore, subjective evidence is assembled based on individual views. The very reason why I chose these elementary teachers as my participants is because I knew them for quite a long time. This is how knowledge is known through the subjective experiences of people. It becomes important, then, to conduct studies in the "field," where the participants live and work, these are important contexts for

understanding what the participants are saying. The longer researchers stay in the "field" or get to know the participants, the more they "know what they know" from firsthand information. For example, good phenomenology requires a prolonged stay at the research site (Wolcott, 2008a). In short, the researcher tries to minimize the "distance" or "objective separateness" (Guba Lincoln, 1988, p. 94) between himself or herself and those being researched. Axiology. This assumption characterizes qualitative research. How does the researcher implement this assumption in practice? In a qualitative study, the inquirers admit the value-laden nature of the study and actively report their values and biases as well as the value-laden nature of information gathered from the field. This means that the result of this study was shared with the school where I am currently working. We say that they "position themselves" in a study. In an interpretive biography, for example, the researcher's presence is apparent in the text, and the author admits that the stories voiced represent an interpretation and presentation of the author as much as the subject of the study (Denzin, 1989a). I believe that I am more qualified to conduct this study since I have ample experience teaching in elementary school.

2.2. *Qualitative Assumptions*—The researcher made these qualitative assumptions that consist of the methods used in the process of qualitative research (Creswell 2003). The procedures used by the researcher are inductive and are based on the researcher's own experience in collecting and analyzing data. The research here is the product of the values of the researcher. Through an inductive approach, raw textual data is condensed into a brief, summary format. Clear links are established between research objectives and summary findings derived from raw data. A framework of the underlying structure of experiences or processes that

are evident from the raw data is developed. A phenomenological study describes the meaning of lived experiences of individuals about a concept or phenomenon (Creswell, 2003) was used in this study. A phenomenological study intends to understand and describe an event from the point of view of the participants. A key characteristic of this approach is to study how members of a group or community interpret themselves, the world, and life around them (Mertens, 2005). The purpose of this study in exploring the challenges of implementing play-based learning in elementary classrooms. Collectively, these results may provide foundational

information to guide the district in addressing the local issue. Administrators might benefit from this information as it might enable them to make informed decisions about what support is needed for teachers in exploring the challenges of implementing play-based learning in grade 1

2.3. Design and Procedure—In the next section, the specific details of the research procedures will be described so future researchers can generalize the results from this study to other situations. Extensive and careful descriptions of the study’s time, place, context, and culture were thoroughly discussed to develop transferability, which is the qualitative parallel to external validity in post-positivist research (Mertens, 2005). This section was: (a) discusses the interview approach, (b) explains the role of the researcher, and lastly, (c) describes the sampling method and ethical considerations. Semi-Structured Interviews. Patton (2015) proposes that researchers conduct interviews to learn what they cannot directly observe. Qualitative interviewing is not used to get answers to questions but to understand the experiences of the participants and the meaning they make of that experience (Seidman, 1988). Generally, qualitative studies use unstructured, open-ended interviews because they allow for the most flexibility and responsiveness to emerging issues for both the participants and interviewer; however, the use of semi-structured interviews is not uncommon and used when the researcher seeks to obtain specific, more focused information (Schwandt, 2001). Semi-structured interviews combine the flexibility of unstructured, open-ended interviews with directionality and an agenda to produce focused, qualitative, textual data (Schensul LeCompte, 71, 1999). This

study collected data using semi-structured interviews to explore how elementary school teachers describe the exploring the challenges of implementing play-based learning in grade 1 classrooms. In addition, this study explores the challenges of implementing play-based learning in grade 1 classrooms, appear to have experienced in the areas of building background knowledge, interactions, and application.

study collected data using semi-structured interviews to explore how elementary school teachers describe the exploring the challenges of implementing play-based learning in grade 1 classrooms. This includes understanding the benefits of play-based learning, designing appropriate learning experiences, and assessing learning outcomes. To ensure that the same information was collected from all the participants, an interview guide was used. The interview guide included open-ended questions and topics to help structure the interview, but when needed, the interviewer also explored, probed, and asked additional questions to clarify and expand on a particular topic. The interview guide helped make interviewing across several different participants more systematic and comprehensive by defining in advance the issues to be explored (Patton, 2015). The open-ended questions were framed in a way, so the participants could represent their views and perspectives in their own words and terms, in addition to taking the questions in any direction that they chose (Patton, 2015). Since qualitative research studies subjects in their natural setting, all interviews except one took place using a face-to-face format at a time convenient for the participants. All interview sessions were tape-recorded for the purposes of transcription. When needed, the researcher used follow-up interviews after transcription to clarify meaning or explore areas in more depth.

2.4. Research Participants—The study includes twelve (12) participants from the public

elementary school faculty, all of whom are currently teaching during the 2022-2023 school

year. The participants will take part in an in-depth interview (IDI). The researcher used purposive sampling, also known as judgment, selective, or subjective sampling. This is a sampling technique in which the researcher relies on their judgment when choosing members of the population to participate in the study. This survey sampling method requires researchers to have prior knowledge about the purpose of their studies to properly choose and approach eligible participants to be conducted (Denzin, 2017). The study includes elementary school teachers from selected public schools in Calinan District Division of Davao City. The participants are described as licensed professional teachers living in Davao City with at least three years of teaching experience.

The researcher is engaged with communi-

2.5. *Data Collection*—Before data gathering, I was asked for the endorsement from the Dean of the Graduate School to pursue the study. After the permissions are approved by the school division Superintendent and the school principals of the target participants, the researcher will talk to the participants to acquaint them with the purpose of the study. I agreed with the participants on the most convenient date and time for the interview. To begin the interview, I asked the participants to read the respondents' consent and have them sign the consent form after they were briefed on the purpose of the study and agreed to the terms and conditions. The researcher emphasized to the respondents that they were allowed to ask questions to clarify any matter regarding the study and asked for their consent to record the conversation with the assurance that everything would be handled with utmost confidentiality. During the in-depth interview, I was able to gather the feelings, reactions, observations, and experiences of the teachers regarding the impact of sleep deprivation on the

ties like the Public Schools academic community, teachers, parents, and basic education students since I am a teacher in one of the public schools in Calinan District, Division of Davao City is composed of quite diverse people; thus, the researcher is sensitive to and respects the cultural, traditional, and religious practices of the community. The guide questions were the instrument for gathering qualitative data in the second phase. On the other hand, proper protocol and seeking approval from the principal of the public schools as my target participants were observed. Moreover, the significant personas in the public-school organizational landscape and other stakeholders may benefit from the study's output because they are the recipients of the data regarding knowledge about project-based learning instructional practices in education.

personality development of pupils. The interview also involved gathering information about the obstacles and challenges that the teachers encounter during home visitations. I was also aiming to gather significant information on exploring play-based learning strategies. I am focusing on elementary teachers to improve the personality development of pupils and interventions that help bridge the gap in understanding, making teaching and learning more realistic experiences for the pupils and teachers. In analyzing the collected data, the participants' narratives will be transcribed. According to Koontz and Weinrich (2000), the process and narratives do not need to be transcribed verbatim if the transcription captures the essence of what the participants were communicating. The respective participants will validate individual transcriptions of the interview. To verify and revalidate the gathered data, the researcher will conduct a focus group discussion to validate and triangulate the information. Corrections may be made based on the participants' feedback to ensure that the fundamental meaning of the

phenomenon is accurately conveyed. The study will collect data from interviews, field notes, and recorded videos, using in-depth interviews and focus group discussions. Field notes will be taken to record nonverbal communication and participants' interactions with the environment. The questionnaire will include a combination of closed and open-ended questions, administered orally by the researcher. The interviews will be semi-structured, employing open-ended questions based on an interview guide. Data will be gathered through field notes, voice recordings, or cellphone videos during the interviews with participants. A piloted interview questionnaire was used with all participants. Twelve participants were interviewed in two sessions lasting 45 to 60 minutes each due to their schedules. The interval between interviews was, on average, one day. Interview questions were based on the study's four research questions, which explored participants' viewpoints. Follow-up questions will also be made to clarify ambiguous comments and discrepant data. In four instances, participants preferred to discuss the ambiguities over attributes of high quality. In a qualitative phenomenological study, the research data involved the researcher spending as much time as possible with the teachers at the high schools to gain an in-depth understanding of the elementary teachers in their everyday lives. Participant observations of the behaviors, beliefs, traditions, culture, social, and emotional interactions were recorded in a journal at the end of each day. In-depth interviews were conducted in field settings, and were either recorded and transcribed, and/or summarized in the journal. As an active participant in the research process, the researcher constantly evaluated her role and her relationship with participants to develop an understanding and interpretation of the basic education teacher's social and emotional worlds (Unger, 2005). This resulted in an evolving research process both in terms of the direction and type of data derived and in terms of a personal transformation for the researcher (Parker, 2005). The evolution of the research as a relational transformation between a researcher with openness to a new experience and a community of participants cannot be overemphasized. The results of this could not have been foreseen at the inception of this study (Parker, 2005). The study took place at an academic institution that had undergone changes in its teaching methods. The researcher, who had prior experience as an elementary school teacher, had the opportunity to gather demographic information and meet with as many residents as possible. The goal was to gain an initial understanding of the community culture through participant observation. All participants provided informed consent before being interviewed. The questionnaires were translated by the researcher into the language commonly used by the participants. Data collection methods were diverse. Yin (2003) stated that the main characteristic of phenomenological qualitative research is the use of various data collection methods to ensure the trustworthiness of the report. Multiple data sources help in gaining a clearer understanding of the data being studied (Creswell, 2008, 2009; Glesne, 2011; Merriam, 2009). Data will be collected from interviews, field notes, and recorded videos obtained through in-depth interviews and focus group discussions. Field notes will record nonverbal communication and participants' interactions with the environment. The questionnaire consisted of a mix of closed- and open-ended questions, which the researcher delivered orally. The interviews were semi-structured and utilized open-ended questions based on an interview guide. Data was generated through field notes, a voice recorder, or cellphone videos during participant interviews. Twelve participants were interviewed in two sessions of 45 minutes to 60 minutes each because of their schedules. The average interval between interviews was one day. Interview questions were based on the study's four research questions, which aimed

to explore participants' viewpoints. Follow-up questions were also asked to clarify ambiguous comments and discrepant data. In four in-

stances, participants chose to discuss ambiguities rather than attributes of high quality.

2.6. *Data Analysis*—Qualitative data analysis begins with organizing, reducing, and describing the collected data (Schwandt, 2001). Unlike quantitative analysis, there are no prescribed formulas for qualitative analysis. Marshall and Rossman (2006) remind researchers that qualitative analysis does not proceed linearly and is not neat. However, good practice and procedures enhance the credibility of qualitative research. In this last section, the data analysis procedures were explained, and the steps taken to ensure the results from this study are credible, transferable, dependable, and authentic were thoroughly described. To guide the data analysis, the researcher used the seven phases of data analysis described by Marshall and Rossman (2006) to reduce data, create manageable pieces, allow for interpretation, and find meaning in the words of the participants. The seven phases included (a) organizing the data, (b) immersion in the data, (c) generating categories and themes, (d) coding the data, (e) offering interpretations through analytic memos, and (f) searching for alternative understandings (Marshall Rossman, 2006). Data analysis first begins with organizing the data. The organization of the data involved keeping information provided by each participant separate and in sequence with the order of the interviews. The process of organizing the data allowed it to remain manageable, easily accessible, and readily available. The digital audio files from the interviews were carefully transcribed into written form. Electronic folders were established to create an organization for the data collected from each participant. Next, the researcher became familiar with the data through extensive reading of the interviews to gain an understanding of the content. This involved reading through

the interviews at least three times. Following Hatch's (2002) recommendations for qualitative analysis, the researcher created a sheet of notes for each participant. The summary sheets were a quick way to refer to the original data as the data analysis continued (Hatch, 2002). After the initial readings, Hatch (2002) recommends researchers read data through completely with one typology in mind. Patton (2015) defines typologies as classification systems made up of categories that divide some aspects of the world into parts. According to Hatch (2002), typologies are generated from theory, common sense, or research objectives. For this study, the researcher used the typologies or themes from the literature review as the constructs through which to view the data. After reading through the data with each constructor typology in mind, the researcher coded the data into five categories from the literature by taking excerpts of text from the data and identifying it within a particular category. After everything was coded, the researcher read through the data again while writing analytic memos on her thoughts and insights and began the process of offering interpretations. During this stage, the researcher began to interpret the data to find significance and meaning in the teachers' instructional experiences through pulling salient themes, reoccurring ideas, and patterns of belief that resonated collectively throughout the interviews. The offering of interpretations began following the emergence of themes in the data. Marshall and Rossman (2006) believed this part of the data analysis brings meaning to the themes and categories and allows the researcher to develop links between the interviews. The researcher began interpreting the data to find significance and meaning in exploring the challenges of im-

plementing play-based learning in elementary classrooms. Rossman and Marshall (2006) remind researchers that alternate explanations al-

ways exist within the data. Before moving forward, the researcher stopped and evaluated the findings for other plausible explanations.

2.7. *Analytical Framework*—The challenges of implementing play-based learning in elementary classrooms were explored within an analytical framework. This approach is considered one of the best pedagogical methods for teaching elementary pupils, as it considers the learners' personalities and inclinations for growth and development. The effective teaching and learning process involves addressing the challenges of implementing play-based learning in elementary classrooms, which greatly interests teachers as it affects the pupils' learning experiences. This exploration can provide new insights and hope for similar situations or cases in the future. The experiences were analyzed to extract their insights and emotions to make a difference in the educational system. Both aimed to provide information on the unfolding stories of teachers as they explored the challenges of implementing play-based learning in elementary classrooms. The data collected during interviews was transcribed, organized, and reviewed to identify patterns and themes. Because this study involved human participants, informed consent was obtained for ethical purposes. The researcher assured us that the study was conducted thoroughly and accurately. Specifically, in qualitative data analysis, findings were identified, confirmed, or rejected as appropriate. Additionally, data transcriptions were provided to the participants to ensure precision. As a result, the researcher ensured that the research outcomes were reasonably available and accessible to the Department of Education, teachers, students, parents, and the community. Following signing consent forms, exploring the challenges of implementing play-based learning in elementary classrooms using semi-structured in-depth interviews. Data was organized and analyzed.

The researcher rigorously examined these units of meaning to elicit the essence of meaning within the holistic context. The entire interview transcript should be added, and anything that might have been left out should be added (Mazuwelics, 2018). Thematic Content Analysis. This was used in interpreting the responses made by the key participants in exploring the challenges of implementing play-based learning in elementary classrooms. Their responses were processed and conducted through analyses. Transcripts were coded in considerable detail with the focus shifting back and forth from the key claims of the participants to the researcher's interpretation of the meaning of the responses and subjectively interpreted. Meanwhile, the notes that may be obtained from in-depth interview may be transcribed immediately. The researcher may be looking for common themes that may be found among the responses to each question. In this phase, the researcher may use thematic analysis in analyzing the gathered data. Their responses were processed and conducted through analysis. Transcripts were coded in considerable detail with the focus shifting back and forth from the key claims of the participants to the researcher's interpretation of the meaning of the responses and subjectively interpreted. Meanwhile, the notes that may be obtained from in-depth interview may be transcribed immediately. The researcher may be looking for common themes that may be found among the responses to each question. Environmental Triangulation. Triangulation analysis is a tool developed by Margaret Schuler to help advocates perform a strategic analysis of the issues they are working on. The tool looks at three different aspects: content, structure, and culture. Triangular analysis is a technique for both analyzing and

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study

finding answers to a problem, structured around structure, content and culture in the policy system was done through transcribing, member checking and triangulation. The entire interview transcript and add anything that might have been left out. The information may be shared with the participants in taking circle to ensure we interpreted the data correctly using triangulation analysis. The researcher must possess trustworthiness and credibility to achieve a truthful and productive result in a qualitative study. With this, the researcher religiously followed the requirements (Mazuwelics, 2018). This study exploring the challenges of implementing play-based learning in elementary classrooms will be used peer debriefing to play the role is asking tough questions about the data collection, data analysis, and data interpretations (Newton Rudestam, 2001). Challenges to implementing play-based learning: Teachers may face challenges such as a lack of resources or support from administrators and parents. Understanding these challenges can help to inform strategies for ad-

ressing them and supporting teachers in implementing play-based learning (Lee Lim, 2020; Tuomi-Gröhn Katajavuori, 2021). The relationship between teacher beliefs and attitudes and children’s learning outcomes: Teachers’ beliefs and attitudes towards play-based learning can impact children’s learning outcomes, such as academic achievement and social-emotional development. Understanding this relationship can help to inform the importance of promoting positive teacher beliefs and attitudes toward play-based learning (Lin Chao, 2021; Patrick et al., 2020). Strategies for promoting positive teacher beliefs and attitudes towards play-based learning: Various strategies can be used to promote positive teacher beliefs and attitudes, such as providing professional development opportunities, engaging in collaborative planning and reflection, and providing resources and support. Understanding these strategies can inform efforts to promote the implementation of play-based learning in elementary classrooms (Hsu et al., 2021; Kwon et al., 2020).

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presented the results of the data analysis and the discussion of the results of the study, which focused on exploring the perceptions and practices of junior high school teachers towards student-centered learning was gathered to specifically; this study sought to answer the following questions: What is the lived experience of teachers in the implementation of play-based learning in elementary classrooms? How do teachers cope to explore the implementation of play-based learning in elementary classrooms? In my upcoming discussion, I want to clarify the symbols I've used to represent the quotes from the participants in the study. I assigned codes to the participants in the research interviews. Their answers revolved around the three research questions of the study. I transcribed their responses verbatim, translated them into English, encoded them, and summarized them in a matrix, resulting in a schema.

]The lived experience of teachers in the implementation of play-based learning in elementary classrooms

Teachers' experiences in individualized reading intervention for struggling readers highlight the importance of personalized, data-driven instruction, flexibility, and a supportive learning environment. Common to all, the re-

sults of the study in line with this phenomenon reveal that success often comes from a combination of effective strategies, ongoing assessment, and a commitment to meeting the unique needs of each student.

3.0.1. teachers' beliefs about play-based learning—Teachers' beliefs about play-based learning are a critical emerging theme in understanding their lived experiences with this pedagogical approach in elementary classrooms. These beliefs significantly influence how teachers implement play-based strategies, adapt to their roles as facilitators of learning, and interact with students, parents, and colleagues. Teachers who view play as an educational tool are more likely to integrate it effectively, fostering environments that promote cognitive, so-

cial, and emotional development, while those with traditional views may struggle, hindering the approach's benefits. Additionally, teachers' convictions about play-based learning shape their advocacy and ability to build supportive communities around this method. That is why aligning teachers' beliefs with the principles of play-based learning is essential for its successful adoption, highlighting the need for research and professional development that addresses and reshapes these beliefs to enhance student learning and development.

3.0.2. Lack of Parental Involvement—Building strong communication and collaboration with parents or caregivers is crucial in individualized interventions. Some parents may not be actively involved, making supporting the child's reading progress outside of school chal-

lenging. In this regard, the Center for Effective Services (2016) sees parental involvement in reading interventions for struggling learners as crucial to a child's educational success. However, this does not seem to be a reality in the setup where the interviewed participants are situated.

3.0.3. attitudes towards play-based learning—

The growing interest in play-based learning within elementary classrooms reflects a broader shift in educational philosophy towards more holistic and child-centered approaches. Play-based learning, which integrates play into the academic curriculum, is increasingly recognized for its potential to enhance cognitive, social, and emotional development in children. This method supports the idea that learning is most effective when it is engaging and enjoyable, fostering a love for learning that can last a lifetime. As a result, teachers' attitudes towards play-based learning are pivotal because they directly influence how these methods are implemented in the classroom. Positive attitudes can lead to more creative and effective integration of play into daily lessons, which can, in turn, support better educational outcomes for students.

3.0.4. Implementation of play-based learning in elementary classrooms—The implementation of play-based learning in elementary classrooms has emerged as a significant theme in the lived experiences of teachers due to its profound impact on both pedagogical practices and student outcomes. Play-based learning, which integrates play into the curriculum as a central component of the educational process, allows for a more holistic approach to child development. Teachers report that this method fosters creativity, critical thinking, and social skills, which are essential for the comprehensive growth of young learners. Furthermore, play-based learning aligns with contemporary educational theories that emphasize the importance of engaging students in meaningful, active learning experiences. This approach not only makes learning more enjoyable for students but also enhances their intrinsic motivation and engagement with the material, leading to deeper understanding and retention of knowledge.

Moreover, the shift towards play-based

The lived experiences of teachers who implement play-based learning are crucial in understanding the practical challenges and benefits of this approach. Teachers' perceptions and attitudes towards play-based learning are shaped by their experiences, training, and the outcomes they observe in their students. As play-based learning becomes more prominent, there is a growing need to explore these experiences to identify best practices and areas for improvement. This exploration can help in addressing any skepticism or resistance among educators, providing insights into how to support and train teachers effectively. Ultimately, the focus on teachers' attitudes and experiences underscores the importance of their role in transforming educational practices to better meet the developmental needs of young learners.

learning reflects broader educational trends and policy changes that advocate for more child-centered and developmentally appropriate practices in early education. Teachers navigating this transition often encounter both opportunities and challenges, which shape their lived experiences in unique ways. The move away from traditional, rote learning methods towards a more flexible and dynamic classroom environment requires teachers to adapt their instructional strategies and classroom management techniques. They must balance curriculum goals with the spontaneous and exploratory nature of play. This evolving pedagogical landscape underscores the need for ongoing professional development and support for teachers, ensuring they are equipped to implement play-based learning effectively. As a result, the theme of play-based learning in the lived experiences of teachers highlights not only the benefits for student learning but also the critical role of teacher adaptation and resilience in educational innovation.

Fig. 3. Thematic Framework of teachers in the implementation of play-based learning in elementary classrooms

3.1. *Coping mechanisms of the teachers with the implementation of play-based learning in elementary classrooms*—The second objective of this study is for the teachers to cope with the implementation of play-based learning in elementary classrooms. Based on the interview data gathered from the teachers’ coping mechanisms with the challenges teachers explore in the implementation of play-based learning in elementary classrooms, the three major themes are the impact of play-based learning on student outcomes, Play-based learning, and academic achievement, and Play-based learning and curriculum goals

3.1.1. *the impact of play-based learning on student outcomes*—Play-based learning has been proven to be a significant way to improve student outcomes, especially in cognitive, social, and emotional development. Integrating play into the curriculum allows children to explore subjects in an exciting and hands-on manner. Through this approach, children can naturally develop their problem-solving and critical thinking skills as they interact with materials, peers, and their environment. Research indicates that play-based education enhances creativity and imagination by providing a safe space for children to experiment with new ideas and take risks. Additionally, cooperative play encourages pro-social skills such as empathy, communication, and cooperation. The play-based teaching method is essential for primary education as these basic skills determine future success.

For successful implementation of play-based learning, teachers need to shift from strict traditional teaching strategies to more flexible, student-centered approaches. Teachers should develop curricula that strike a balance between guided and unstructured play while meeting desired learning outcomes. This means setting up spaces that are resource-intensive and adaptable enough to match pupils’ needs and interests. Instead of controlling the course of the game, teachers should encourage it.

3.1.2. *Play-based learning and academic achievement*—

The integration of play-based learning in elementary classrooms has garnered significant attention due to its potential to enhance academic achievement. Grounded in the theories of educational psychologists such as Jean Piaget and Lev Vygotsky, this approach emphasizes play as a crucial medium for learning. Piaget's theory of cognitive development suggests that children learn best through hands-on experiences and active exploration, while Vygotsky emphasizes the social context of learning, proposing that play allows children to internalize and understand complex social interactions (Bodrova Leong, 2007). These theoretical foundations support the notion that play is not merely a break from learning but an integral component of the educational process that fosters cognitive and social development. Empirical studies support this, showing that play-based environments enhance language development, literacy skills, and mathematical understanding (Miller

Almon, 2009).

Play-based learning also promotes critical thinking, problem-solving, collaboration, and communication among peers, creating a classroom environment that values teamwork and collective problem-solving (Weisberg et al., 2013). Despite challenges such as the perception that play detracts from instructional time, play-based learning can align with educational standards and outcomes when teachers receive adequate professional development and support (Hirsh-Pasek et al., 2009). In conclusion, play-based learning significantly enhances academic achievement and supports the cognitive, social, and emotional development of children, making a compelling case for its adoption in elementary education. As educational policies continue to evolve, recognizing and supporting the value of play-based learning will ensure that children benefit from this innovative approach.

3.1.3. Play-based learning and curriculum goals—Play-based learning effectively aligns with and enhances curriculum goals in elementary education by integrating academic objectives into engaging, interactive activities. This approach is supported by educational theories from Jean Piaget and Lev Vygotsky, which highlight the importance of hands-on experiences and social interactions in cognitive development (Bodrova Leong, 2007). Empirical evidence shows that play-based learning environments foster language development, literacy, and numeracy skills, essential components of elementary curricula (Miller Almon,

2009). For instance, activities such as storytelling, role-playing, and games involving counting or pattern recognition can meet curriculum standards while maintaining student engagement and motivation. Additionally, play-based learning promotes critical thinking, problem-solving, and collaboration, skills that are integral to academic success and lifelong learning (Weisberg et al., 2013). Despite some concerns that play may detract from instructional time, it can be strategically designed to complement educational outcomes, ensuring a well-rounded and effective learning experience for young students (Hirsh-Pasek et al., 2009).

3.2. Educational management insights are drawn from the study—The following educational insights drawn from the participants' narratives are crucial in a qualitative research undertaking. This part of the study outlines these insights as reflective of the views and perspectives on the issues at hand. Some of the participants' revelations and contemplation were significant factors in reading development. Some of the participants cited the following insights from their experiences.

Fig. 4. Teachers’ coping mechanism to explore implementing play-based learning in elementary classrooms

3.2.1. *classroom organization and materials*—In the Department of Education, effective classroom organization and suitable materials are paramount for facilitating play-based learning. A well-structured classroom should offer designated areas that cater to various types of play, ensuring children have opportunities for imaginative play, constructive play, and sensory exploration. For instance, a cozy reading corner with comfortable seating and a diverse selection

of books can encourage literacy-based play, while a block area stocked with building blocks of different shapes and sizes fosters constructive play. Additionally, sensory stations equipped with materials like sand, water, and playdough provide avenues for sensory exploration and experimentation. Accessible materials that are age-appropriate and aligned with learning objectives are crucial for stimulating children’s creativity and curiosity, thereby enhancing their engagement and learning experiences.

3.2.2. *limitations and critical analysis of literature*—Despite the growing interest in play-based learning, the literature reveals several limitations that warrant critical analysis. One significant challenge is the lack of standardized assessment tools tailored to measure learning outcomes in play-based environments accurately. Traditional assessment methods may not fully capture the breadth and depth of skills developed through play, leading to difficulties in evaluating

its effectiveness. Moreover, while anecdotal evidence and small-scale studies support the benefits of play-based learning, there is a need for more rigorous empirical research to establish its efficacy across diverse educational contexts. Addressing these limitations requires interdisciplinary collaboration among educators, researchers, and policymakers to develop comprehensive frameworks for assessing and promoting play-based approaches effectively.

3.2.3. *the importance of child-centered learning*—

Fig. 5. Educational management insights are drawn from the study

In play-based learning, the centrality of child-directed exploration and discovery cannot be overstated. By placing children at the forefront of their learning experiences, educators empower them to take ownership of their education and develop essential skills such as problem-solving, communication, and collaboration. Child-centered learning encourages autonomy and self-regulation, allowing children to pursue their interests and follow their natu-

ral curiosity. This approach is aligned with the Department of Education’s emphasis on promoting holistic development and lifelong learning skills among students. By nurturing a supportive learning environment that respects children’s voices and choices, play-based learning fosters a love for learning that extends beyond the classroom, preparing students to become active, engaged citizens in an ever-changing world.

4. Implications and Future Directions

This chapter presents a brief overview of the study followed by implications based on its findings. Future directions in culturally responsive teachers through the lens of classroom advisers are also discussed here. The target population for this study will be the twelve (12) participants from the line-up of public elementary school faculty, an elementary school unit, who are still teaching during the school year 2022-2023. The participants will join for an in-depth interview (IDI). The researcher considered the faculty from selected public elementary school teachers still teaching. A sample of twelve (12) elementary school teachers was purposefully selected from this population.

4.1. *Implications*—The research highlights play-based learning strategies and explores how these strategies enhance the overall pedagogical approach in elementary class-

rooms. This could involve assessing whether play-based methods lead to increased student engagement, motivation, and a deeper understanding of the subject matter. Teachers need more opportunities for professional development in

the realm of student-centered learning. Implications suggest that investing in training programs and resources is essential to help educators effectively navigate these challenges. Teachers may benefit from professional development and training on recognizing and addressing sleep-related issues. Explore how play-based learning strategies align with and enhance the existing elementary school curriculum. Researchers

can investigate how these strategies can be integrated into current curricular standards and whether this integration improves learning outcomes. Study the development of appropriate assessment tools to measure the effectiveness of play-based learning. This includes formative and summative assessment methods to gauge student progress and the impact of play-based approaches on academic achievement.

4.2. Future Directions—These responses highlight the potential future directions and actions that can help teachers address the challenges of balancing to develop and validate innovative assessment methods better suited to measure the holistic development fostered by play-based learning. Explore alternative methods, such as portfolios, peer assessments, and self-assessments, that capture the richness of student experiences. Future directions should involve more active engagement with exploring ways to advocate for policy changes that support and fund play-based learning in elementary education. Research can focus on strategies for influencing educational policy at the district, state, and national levels. In the future, we should explore and implement more flexible assessment models that align with how classroom layouts, materials, and resources influence the effectiveness of play-based strategies. This may require a shift away from traditional exams and a focus on alternative ways of evaluating student progress. Future directions should include changes in administrative policies to provide stronger support for teachers. School leaders

should champion Research can identify barriers, misconceptions, and ways to address concerns to promote wider acceptance of play-based approaches and implement policies that encourage a more balanced approach. We should encourage research into the effectiveness of student-centered learning in junior high schools. Future directions should involve data-driven decision-making to assess the impact of these practices and guide further improvements. As the field of education continues to evolve, these future research directions can help advance our understanding of play-based learning strategies in elementary education and contribute to the development of evidence-based practices that benefit students and educators. Future directions should involve customized teacher training programs to address challenges. Not all teachers face the same obstacles, and personalized training can help them overcome their challenges. By exploring these future research directions, scholars can contribute to a deeper understanding of the challenges and opportunities related to play-based learning in elementary education and support the professional development and well-being of elementary teachers.

5. References

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